

Rac-3p

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-114-rac-5%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	48	Acq. Method Set:	5%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 114 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/4/2021 10:21:16 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:15:11 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.762	2329916	49.61	147157
2	13.434	2366227	50.39	142783

Asy-3p (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-115-2-5%-IA	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0904
Vial:	70	Acq. Method Set:	5%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 2 115 2
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	18.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	9/4/2021 10:42:54 PM CST		
Date Processed:	10/26/2021 10:13:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	12.786	236368	5.04	15203
2	13.426	4451607	94.96	268885